

Metadata Documentation for the PV Suitability Analysis Tool

Title:

Dynamic Tool for Identifying Spatial Suitability of Buildings for Photovoltaic (PV) Energy Systems

Description:

This tool is designed to analyze and visualize the suitability of buildings within the Canton of Geneva for hosting photovoltaic (PV) energy systems. Using spatial and attribute data from official sources, along with an algorithm developed in the scope of a PhD thesis, the tool provides public authorities and researchers with an interactive interface to assess potential PV installations at the building level. This enables data-driven decision-making in renewable energy deployment and sustainable urban planning.

Authors:

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Date of Creation:

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Version:

1.0

License:

Open-Source License (Developed in Python), incorporating publicly available data and a customized PV suitability assessment algorithm

I. Data Sources

1. Shapefile Layer (OCEN_SOLAIRE_PV_BATIMENT.shp)

- **Source:** Geographic Information System of the Canton of Geneva (SITG)
- **URL:** https://ge.ch/sitg/sitg_catalog/sitg_donnees
- **Description:** Contains spatial data on buildings within the Canton of Geneva, including structural attributes and classifications relevant to PV suitability.

2. Filtered CSV Dataset (filtered_geneva_data.csv)

- **Source:** Derived from a broader LiDAR dataset covering the Greater Geneva Area, which includes French municipalities, municipalities in the district of Nyon (Canton of Vaud), and municipalities in the Canton of Geneva.
- **Processing:** Filtered to include only buildings located in the Canton of Geneva, with a focus on attributes relevant to PV system suitability, such

as geographic coordinates, available roof area, heritage classification, and potential PV capacity.

II. Features

The tool provides an interactive map interface with the following features:

- **Spatial Filtering:** Enables selection of buildings based on their suitability for PV installations within the Canton of Geneva.
 - **Interactive Tooltips:** Each building's tooltip displays key attributes, including:
 - Identification Number
 - Category Class
 - Heritage Level
 - Available Roof Area (m²)
 - Potential Capacity (MWp)
 - Initial Investment (indicating "Not economically viable" where applicable)
 - Optimal Solar PV Installation Area (m²)
 - CO₂ Emissions Avoided (kgCO₂/year)
 - **Background Options:** Users can toggle between different map backgrounds (dark, light grey, medium grey) for better visualization.
 - **Algorithm for PV Suitability Analysis:** A custom algorithm is included to assess each building's PV suitability, based on the structure's attributes and spatial data.
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III. Intended Use and Applications

This tool assists public authorities and researchers in evaluating the potential for PV installations on a building-by-building basis within Geneva. It aids in sustainable urban planning, supporting informed decisions on resource allocation and environmental impacts, and is adaptable for large-scale PV deployment analyses.

IV. Technical Details

- **Programming Language:** Python, using folium, geopandas, pandas
 - **Data Formats:** Shapefile (.shp), CSV (.csv)
 - **Output Format:** Interactive HTML map
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V. Access and Repository

The complete tool, along with metadata, documentation, sample outputs, and the algorithm code, is available in the open-access repository Zenodo for further scientific contributions.

The repository includes:

- Full source code
- Processed datasets for Geneva
- Sample map outputs
- Detailed documentation on installation and usage

VI. Usage Instructions

1. **Data Preparation:** Ensure the shapefile (OCEN_SOLAIRE_PV_BATIMENT.shp) and CSV dataset (filtered_geneva_data.csv) are in the working directory.
2. **Execution:** Run the code in a Python environment to generate an HTML file with the interactive map.
3. **Interactivity:** Use the HTML file to explore buildings by PV suitability, toggle map backgrounds, and view specific building attributes through tooltips.
4. **Customization:** The tool allows flexibility for adding additional features, enabling it to be tailored for specific territorial needs.

VII. Future Extensions

The tool's code and algorithm are adaptable, allowing for new features or datasets to be integrated, such as additional suitability criteria or extended geographic coverage. Contributions from the scientific community are encouraged to support the tool's continuous enhancement and application in diverse regions.